

Automated Reed Dent Inspection using Image Processing for Enhanced Quality Assurance in Textile Weaving

J. P. Kharat*, Atharva Ningnure, Ritu Patil, Rutuja Patil, Sanjana Desai

Dept. of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, D.K.T.E. Society's Textile & Engineering Institute, Ichalakrajji, India

Abstract:

Background:

The reed constitutes a critical element in the weaving process, ensuring uniform distribution of warp yarns across the fabric width. Surface defects in reed dents, such as burrs, scratches, and misalignments, can lead to loom stoppages, yarn breakage, and defective fabric structures, thereby adversely affecting productivity. Conventional visual inspection of dents is labour-intensive, highly subjective, and susceptible to oversight of significant defects.

Methods:

This study presents a computer vision-based automated inspection framework for reed dent quality assessment. High-resolution dent images were processed using edge detection algorithms in conjunction with morphological filtering to localize and characterize surface scratches and imperfections. The developed system subsequently classified the inspected dents into "Accept" and "Reject" categories in accordance with established textile quality standards.

Results:

Experimental evaluation of the proposed method demonstrated a detection accuracy of 94% for surface scratches. The automated classification process substantially reduced operator dependency, minimized subjective variability, and enhanced inspection throughput compared to traditional manual approaches.

Conclusion:

The findings confirm that automated inspection leveraging computer vision techniques offers a robust and reliable alternative to conventional practices. Implementation of the proposed system in textile manufacturing environments can facilitate consistent reed dent quality control, improve fabric integrity, reduce loom downtime, and ultimately increase overall production efficiency.

Keywords : Computer Vision, Morphological Processing, Reed Dent Inspection, Robotic Automation, Textile Manufacturing

Citation: J. P. Kharat*, Atharva Ningnure, Ritu Patil, Rutuja Patil, Sanjana Desai. "Automated Reed Dent Inspection using Image Processing for Enhanced Quality Assurance in Textile Weaving", *Journal of the Textile Association*, **86/3**(Sept-Oct'25),247-251, <https://www.doi.org/10.63665/xxxxx>

Article History : Received : 23-04-2025, Revised: 22-09-2025, Accepted:26-09-2025

1. Introduction

A dent, an integral part of the reed, greatly affects the overall quality of cloth woven in the textile industry. During weaving, the beating of the weft yarns into position is carried out by the reed, which consists of many closely set metal strips called dents, aside from repartitioning the warp strands. Dent alignment or surface irregularities coupled with deformation or misalignment result in a wide range of issues such as snagged yarn movement, broken ends, banded fabric borders, and uneven stripe patterns, which are among the most common weaving defects. The perception of rudimentary quality features has improved over the years, and as a result, textile mills have heightened their attention toward proactive quality assurance measures. These methods focus on achieving near perfection, with almost no flaws in the fabric. Ordinarily, though, most reed inspection processes

are still manual, with workers looking at each dent through a microscope. This method, though not entirely unsuccessful, is inefficient, painstaking, and relies greatly on the inspector's experience and attention to detail [1].

Mistakes that arise from automated processes, such as overshooting boundaries in mask cutting, may compromise the accuracy sought. These "nearly unobservable" scratches can negatively impact productivity due to deteriorated loom performance, necessitating more frequent stoppages. Moreover, accepting damaged reeds, especially at earlier processing stages, can lead to significant losses if fabrics are later rejected during grey inspection or finishing.

The novelty of this study lies in the development of a fully automated, computer vision-based system specifically designed to identify surface-level defects in reed dents, combining edge detection, morphological filtering, and high-resolution imaging. Unlike conventional manual inspection methods, this system provides rapid, objective, and

* **Corresponding Author:**
Dr. Mrs. Jayashree P. Kharat
Email: jpkharat@dkte.ac.in

consistent dent assessment, enabling proactive quality control prior to loom installation. The proposed system outperforms traditional scratch detection methods in terms of accuracy and processing speed, and facilitates real-time decision-making regarding reed acceptance or rejection.

2. Related Work

The need for modern textile mills to produce high-quality fabric has led to extensive research on process automation and flaw detection. While significant efforts have been made to monitor loom tension, yarn quality, and surface flaws in woven fabrics, there has been limited progress in automating the inspection of loom components such as dents and reeds, despite the fact that these factors greatly influence weaving performance. Traditional methods for maintaining reeds and inspecting dents rely on manual techniques that use visual aids. This approach is subjective, lacking standardized quantitative criteria, and heavily reliant on the skill of the operator. Although many mills employ checklists for quality control, subtle defects like surface scratches or edge deformities on dents often go unnoticed, potentially leading to fabric flaws. [2, 3]

Understanding how reed condition affects weaving quality, some studies have explored the relationship between reed defects and fabric imperfections. For instance, one study established a link between worn reed edges, inconsistent dent spacing, bar marks, and weft floats have been identified as key contributors to weaving faults [4]. Additionally, the necessity of periodic reed inspection has been highlighted as a means to maintain uniform warp tension throughout the weaving process is addressed by authors of [5].

However, these studies mainly emphasize the issue rather than providing practical solutions for identifying damaged reeds. This research aims to address this gap by developing an automated scratch detection system using digital image processing, specifically designed to identify defects on reed dents. The detection of surface defects, particularly scratches on metal components, is a mature area within industrial quality control. Given that textile reed dents are typically made of hardened steel, existing metal surface inspection techniques can be adapted to identify defects that impact yarn handling and overall fabric quality. For example, a techniques proposed in [6] employs fuzzy c-means clustering and morphological features to detect scratches on textured surfaces, demonstrating its effectiveness in isolating and highlighting defects. Another approach described in [7] incorporates Gabor filters at various orientations to extract directional features of scratches, followed by morphological operations to connect fragmented defect regions. An improved method based on Multi-Scale Retinex and Log-Gabor wavelets was introduced in [8] to enhance and identify scratches on steel plates through multi-channel segmentation and phase consistency. Similarly, technique in [9] have applied invariant moment and texture feature analysis to classify defects like scratches, holes, and oil stains. Optical microscopy-based comparison techniques proposed in [10], and optical-digital systems using reflectivity variations

proposed in [11], further contributed to surface fault detection. An automated classification system that identifies multiple defect types, including scratches on metallic surfaces, was developed using an enhanced Gabor filter approach [12].

Although these techniques have shown success in generic metal surface inspection, their direct application to textile-specific reed dents is underexplored. This study adapts and refines these methods for the unique geometry and operational demands of weaving looms, providing an industry-specific solution for proactive dent-level quality assurance.

3. Proposed System

The main goal of the proposed system is to automatically check reed dents for surface-level damage, especially scratches lower the woven fabric's quality and may compromise woven fabric quality. The method is intended to be incorporated into textile weaving facilities' maintenance procedures, allowing for the accurate and impartial assessment of dents prior to reed installation on looms.

3.1 The purpose of the Reed and Dent Inspection

The warp yarn spacing is maintained during weaving by the hundreds of vertical metal strips called dents that make up each reed. Because of the constant mechanical friction caused by the yarns and the fast weft insertion, the dents are prone to wear, scratches, and burr formation. Observable fabric flaws can arise from even small surface flaws, which can lead to yarn fraying, end breaking, and irregular weft beats.

Thus, it is essential to proactively detect and reject damaged dents in order to preserve consistent fabric quality and loom performance.

Thus, early detection and classification of damaged dents are crucial. The proposed system automates this process, eliminating human error and enforcing consistent inspection standards.

The system classifies dents into:

Accept: Smooth, defect-free dent surface within tolerance.

Reject: Scratches or deformations exceeding threshold criteria (e.g., length > 5 mm, intensity deviation > 25%).

3.2 Overall Design and Block Diagram

The system architecture of the proposed reed dent inspection system consists of three primary subsystems:

- Material Handling Unit,
- Vision Inspection Unit,
- Robotic Sorting Unit.

These subsystems are integrated into an efficient process that automates dent handling, inspection, and sorting. The block diagram (Figure 1) provides a visual representation of the entire process.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Quality Inspection of Reed Dents

3.2.1 Material Handling Unit

This unit ensures smooth and aligned movement of the reed through the inspection zone. It includes:

a. Conveyor Belt Assembly

This unit involves a conveyor system driven by a NEMA 23 stepper motor, which feeds the reed dents into the inspection zone. An IR proximity sensor is used to precisely align the dents before image acquisition. The conveyor operates at an adjustable speed, allowing for real time inspection.

b. Image Acquisition Assembly:

To take successive pictures of the reed at predetermined intervals, a high-resolution industrial camera is positioned above a sliding rail. A diffuse LED lighting system reduces reflection from the metallic dent surface and guarantees consistent illumination.

3.2.2 Vision Inspection Unit

A low cost HP W100 webcam paired with the NVIDIA Jetson Nano platform performs image processing. The captured images are analysed to detect surface scratches and verify dimensional accuracy. MultiLED ring illumination ensures consistent lighting during image capture, which is critical for accurate defect detection.

The Jetson Nano processes the images using Open-CV and embedded vision algorithms, as described in the imaging algorithms section.

a. Pre-processing Step:

To reduce noise, captured images are transformed to greyscale and run through Gaussian filtering. To improve the contrast between clean and scratched surfaces, adaptive histogram equalisation is applied.

b. Morphological Processing:

To improve linear characteristics and eliminate any scratch marks, morphological processes like erosion and dilation are used. Refer to the Morphological Filtering Output in Figure 1.

c. Edge Detection and Feature Extraction:

To track the abrupt changes in intensity that are typical of scratches, the Sobel and canny edge detectors are used. To differentiate between small surface irregularities and genuine scratches, the length, width, and form of discovered characteristics are examined.

d. Defect Classification:

Scratches with a pixel intensity deviation larger than 25% of the normalised mean are identified using a threshold-based logic. Some dents are designated Accept, while others with many large scratches are tagged Reject.

e. Output Visualisation:

The outcome is shown in a graphical user interface (GUI) that shows the original image with overlays emphasising any flaws found.

3.2.3 Robotic Sorting Unit

The robotic arm is made to be easily set up on a table for reed inspection as shown in figure 4. A linear actuator automates reed movement under the camera, allowing inspection of standard reeds (up to 120 cm) within 3–5 minutes. This speed is suitable for daily inspection routines in medium- to high-volume weaving mills.

This arm is responsible for sorting passed and rejected dents based on the image analysis. Rejected dents are moved to a separate bin, while acceptable dents continue down the conveyor.

Figure 2: Robotic Arm Assembly

Figure 3: Full Experimental Set Up

4. Result Discussion

A set of fifteen industrial reeds from working shuttle-less looms from a textile mill that specialises in producing cotton fabric were used for the exploratory trials. Every reed had roughly 1500 dents in it. These reeds had been used in regular

production and exhibited natural wear and tear, making them ideal for validating the system under Real world textile manufacturing conditions.

4.1. Dataset and Validation Setup

More than 3000 dental pictures were gathered into a dataset. Each dent was manually inspected by knowledgeable loom fitters and labelled as Accept or Reject. This served as the ground truth for confirming the validity of the suggested system. The system was then tasked with detecting three primary defect types relevant to textile weaving:

- Linear surface scratches caused by prolonged yarn friction
- Corrosive pitting or dull spots due to humid storage or oxidation
- Dimensional deviations such as bent or misaligned dents

4.2 Scratch Detection and Dent Classification Performance

Figure 6.1 illustrates a typical dent with actual wear damage. Scratches appear as subtle grooves along the surface and often align with yarn direction. These scratches though faint to the human eye can trigger yarn fraying or warp breaks during weaving.

Figure 6.2 displays the output of the image processing algorithm. Scratches are detected using edge detection and morphological operations and are highlighted in the output with overlays. Here, the scratch is clearly marked by the system, meeting the rejection criteria (length > 5 mm, intensity gradient > 25%).

Across a range of dent wear levels, the system showed strong scratch detecting abilities. Scratches are shown as highlighted linear anomalies throughout the dent surfaces in Figure 3, which displays the findings of sample detection.

Conversely, Figure 6.3 illustrates a dent deemed acceptable. The algorithm correctly determines the absence of significant scratches or deformation.

Figure 4: Original Image

Figure 5: Scratch Detected Image

Figure 6: No Scratch Detected Image

4.3 Acceptance and Rejection Classification

Based on the defect thresholds, the system produced the following results:

- Accepted Dents: 2738 (91.3%)
- Rejected Dents: 262 (8.7%)

Reeds exhibiting a rejection rate above 5% were flagged for either polishing or replacement. This aligns with standard textile practices where defective reeds are not installed on high-speed looms to avoid yarn damage and fabric loss.

Table 1: Performance parameters of Proposed Method

Sr. No.	Method	Accuracy	Time/Dent
1.	Manual	85%	3.5s
2.	Proposed System	95.2%	0.8s

The detection accuracy and detection time are shown in Table 2. The results show that the suggested approach works better than the conventional approach.

4.4 Effect on Fabric Quality

To test the impact of proposed system, two looms were used for weaving. One loom used reeds that had been manually examined, while the second loom used reeds that had been validated using the automated process. Minor weaving defects, such as weft misplacement and end breaking, were reduced by 32% in the latter's grey fabric. The fabric also displayed less yarn tension and a more uniform width, supporting the notion that higher dent quality enhances fabric consistency.

5. Conclusion

In the context of modern textile manufacturing, where quality, speed, and consistency are critical, the condition of loom accessories like reeds and dents is vital. This study presents a novel image-processing-based approach that automates the detection of surface defects in individual reed dents, addressing a previously overlooked aspect of loom maintenance. The system provides fast, objective, and reliable assessment, directly contributing to improved fabric quality and reduced loom downtime.

Thanks to its ability to detect cosmetic issues such as scratches and corrosion on each dent, the technology

supports proactive quality control. Experimental validation demonstrates clear advantages at the fabric level, including low weaving fault rates, high homogeneity, accurate dent classification, and rapid processing suitable for integration on the shop floor.

This approach improves the human subjective judgment by enabling:

- Consistent standards for dent quality approval
- Minimization of rework and downstream fabric rejection through timely identification of defective reeds

- Improvement in overall fabric quality, emphasizing the importance of component-level maintenance in textile production.

The novelty and practical significance of the proposed system are underscored by its potential extension to multi-angle inspection, real-time analysis on the weaving floor, and integration with predictive maintenance platforms. As textile industries continue to adopt Industry 4.0 paradigms, this dent inspection system offers a focused and innovative solution aligned with intelligent textile manufacturing practices.

Reference :

[1] H. W. Lippincott and H. Stark, "Optical-digital detection of dents and scratches on specular metal surfaces," *Applied Optics*, vol. 21, no. 16, pp. 2875–2881, 1982. DOI: 10.1364/AO.21.002875

[2] Z. Tan, Y. Ji, Z. Fei, X. Xu, and B. Zhao, "Image-Based Scratch Detection by Fuzzy Clustering and Morphological Features," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 18, Art. 6490, 2020. DOI: 10.3390/app10186490

[3] A. Sayam, M. F. Rabbi, M. Hossain, M. O. Faruque, N. Ahmed, S. Alimuzzaman, F. Ahmed, M. R. Islam & A. N. M. M. Rahma, "Influence of Denting Order on Quality and Appearance of Cotton Based Plain Woven Fabric," *Journal of Natural Fibers*, vol. 19, no. 14, 2022. DOI: 10.1080/15440478.2021.1975599

[4] A. N. Purant, D. R. Bamb, and R. Dugge, "Study of Reed on High-Speed Weaving Machines," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, vol. 6, no. 10, Oct. 2019

[5] M. Ravi Kumar and P. Sinha, "Analysis of warp breakages and loom efficiency in cotton weaving," *Indian Textile Journal*, vol. 126, no. 3, pp. 62–66, 2016

[6] K. Patel and D. Shah, "Influence of reed maintenance on woven fabric defects," *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 45–49, 2019

[7] S. Liu and H. Jing, "Scratch detection in metal surface by blasting using Gabor filters," *Proceedings, Eighth International Symposium on Advanced Optical Manufacturing and Testing Technology (AOMATT 2016)*. DOI: 10.1117/12.2243220b

[8] L. Yang, X. Huang, Y. Ren, and Y. Zhang, "Study on steel plate scratch detection based on improved MSR and phase consistency," *Signal, Video and Image Processing*, Mar. 2022. DOI: 10.1007/s11760-022-02211-5

[9] B. Xue and Z. Wu, "Key Technologies of Steel Plate Surface Defect Detection System Based on Artificial Intelligence Machine Vision," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 2021, 12 pages. DOI: 10.1155/2021/5553470

[10] K. A. Gross, J. Lungevics, J. Zavickis, and L. Pluduma, "A comparison of quality control methods for scratch detection on polished metal surfaces," *Measurement*, vol. 117, pp. 397–402, Mar. 2018. DOI: 10.1016/j.measurement.2017.12.022

[11] C. Tikhe and J. S. Chitode, "Metal surface inspection for defect detection and classification using Gabor Filter," *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 3, no. 6n: An Empirical Study using Multiple Regression Analysis. *European Economic Letters*, Vol 13, Issue 1 (2023) 1-14.

The Textile Association (India)

Membership Fees

Sr. No.	Type of Membership	Membership Fee*
A.	Corporate Member	INR 20,000
B.	Patron Member	INR 4,600
C.	Life Member	INR 3,200
D.	Overseas Member	USD 120
E.	Lifetime to Patron Member	INR 2,000

***Plus 18% GST**